

METHODS FOR TEACHING TRANSLATION

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Annotation: *This article is devoted to the research and review of several translational principles. Without these, the entire translation process could fall apart, and they are regarded as the main supporting pillars of translation. Here, the concept of translation and its fundamental components are discussed and highlighted. An problem that is thoroughly explored in this paper is the necessity of translation approaches for adopting the proper instructional methodologies for translation.*

Key words: *translation, methodology, lexicographers, dictionary, linguistic knowledge, the source language (SL), the target language (TL), teacher, language, metacognitive exercise.*

Introduction. As we know that there are one or more specific purposes of every translation activity, the main aim of translation is to serve as a cross-cultural bilingual communication vehicle among people [4;14]. Many people opined about translation. For example, Chute (1978) cited in Miremadi, (1991:21) vindicated that "Without translation, our world would narrow mercilessly". Nida and Taber (1982:12) remark translating as a process of reproducing in the receptor language the closest natural equivalent of the SL messages first according to meaning and secondly according to style [8;16]. Newmark finds translation as "a craft consisting in the endeavours to replace a written message and/or statement in one language by the same message and/or statement in another language" (Newmark,

1981). Nielson (1994) expresses that lexicographers note, compose and publish dictionaries for both print and online issue. They may work on dictionaries for native speakers, dictionaries for learners of a special language, technical dictionaries (for example law), bilingual dictionaries for native speakers or learners of the language [9;23].

In general, education is a great mission. It is not an easy job; a teacher must put out a lot of work in order to communicate with students in a way that will allow him or her to impart knowledge. On the other hand, teaching translation requires advanced skills because the person doing the teaching must be an expert in the field, capable of approaching the subject matter of translation as both a science and a talent. In other words, he or she must possess two distinct skills, the first of which is the capacity to teach translation as a theoretical subject while also having professional experience in translation as a practical field. Because of this, translation instructors need to be qualified to conduct their jobs (i.e. teaching and translation). A translation teacher must use particular techniques to carry out this role effectively. The teacher of translation must be proficient in both the source language and target language (SL and TL) in order for the quality of his work to be believable.

Methods for Teaching Translation. Teachers must first presume that students have solid linguistic knowledge—both theoretical and practical—as well as a broad cultural multilingual background, both of which they acquired during their first years of college. In other words, in order for students to be qualified to translate in an acceptable manner, teachers must first teach them the theoretical components of translation in detail. In other words, in the first year, they must teach students the theoretical concepts in addition to the fundamentals of translation, starting with how to translate simple sentences and progressing to dealing with paragraphs and texts in a graduate-level manner [7;85]. Gerding-Salas has outlined some recommended methodological procedures at <http://www.translatiojournal.net>. In terms of students' motivation, productivity, and

the caliber of the translated work, I believe that these stages can be quite successful in teaching translation [1]. They are as follows:

1. The content to be translated is chosen by the teacher. The selection of texts must take into account a variety of factors, including the texts' level of difficulty (semantic, cultural, stylistic, etc.), the topic or area of expertise (science and technology, social, institutional, economic, and/or political topics, literary or philosophical works, translation challenges to be overcome, etc.) [5;21].

2. The students, with the help of their teacher, should identify the source, the norm, the type of text, the register, the style, and the intended audience of the selected text after scanning it (scan reading).

3. Students should at least twice read the entire text: To familiarize the student with the subject and help them comprehend the original, the first reading should be thorough and all-inclusive. However, remember that context always determines meaning.

4. The second reading needs to be conceptually more in-depth because students tend to focus on passages where translation issues could arise. This process of pre-editing and evaluating the writing's quality might be referred to as "reading with translation intention" (Reminder: Not all texts are well written). When translating from the original text into the target language, the student should have the right to make corrections in their own version if they find errors (often caused by typos) in the source text. Students should first underline unfamiliar terms when reading with the purpose of translating them, and then they should mentally approach any potential translation challenges in the text with appropriate translation techniques.

5. The material is then divided by the number of pupils in the class, up to a maximum of ten parts. These sections could be paragraphs, columns, pages, or even entire chapters, depending on the text's length and degree of complexity. After then, a reasonable amount of the text is given to each student. To ensure that

a different student starts a translation unit each time, the segment distribution order should be rotated.

6. If the students are already familiar with the subject, they perform a preliminary translation. Since students often transfer SL units of translation to TL units of translation, this first approach to the text will probably lack naturalness (one to-one translation). This initial strategy is frequently presented orally, and suggested annotations may be noted in the margins.

7. Students should study supplementary reading if they are absolutely unfamiliar with the subject. In other words, they should consult a variety of documentation sources before starting the transfer process, especially parallel texts (those that are comparable in content and style) written in the original language. They are able to comprehend the subject at hand more fully as a result.

8. After finishing the "one-to-one" version, the students translate themselves again, this time in writing, using the best techniques for doing so while being faithful to the ideas they are transferring.

9. Each student reads out their own version of the translated text, pausing as needed in between words, while holding the original text in front of them and being sure to maintain the same correlative order of the SL text.

10. Both the teacher and the pupils pay close attention to the reading of each text. When the circumstance calls for comments, suggestions, questions, contributions, etc., everyone should feel free to ask for the section to be read again at the end of a particular sentence as a monitoring activity. The students are required to "defend" their assignments from criticism.

11. Throughout this process, the students and the teacher must establish all required norms in order to ensure that the terminology are uniform and that the final product is coherent and cogent.

12. According to Newmark (1988a), students should be encouraged to make notes and have a discussion about the contributions and remarks that result from this analytical reading of each of the several interpretations put forth.[6;56]

13. As a metacognitive exercise, the students, with the teacher's help, evaluate the translation techniques employed and examine the factors that went into selecting each analyzed criterion: "A translator's competence is fundamentally based on their capacity to discuss translations in an objective manner" (Kussmaul, 1995).

14. After revising and post-editing their segments in light of the entire text, the students turn in the finished product. The assignment must be typed, with double spacing, and on the same pagination as the original.

15. The instructor conducts a last review (second post-edit), provides formative feedback, and makes remarks. On the one hand, the teacher emphasizes finds, "happy" solutions, and creative acts, while on the other hand, she examines process flaws and failures [3;54].

Conclusion. Transcribing a text from one language into another is the process of translation. In order to translate between two different languages, the translator must convert an original text (ST) into a new text (TT) [2;205]. It involves conveying the meaning of a text in the source language with text in the target language that is equal. Translation requires a professional to handle as a process because it is so important as a tool for communication. In other words, the translator must be multilingual because translation involves two separate languages (i.e., professional in SL and TL. This also applies to translator educators. The translator teacher should use specific techniques to carry out this function in order to do it effectively. These techniques ought to work when put into practice. As was already said, there are specific profiles that professors and students in the field of translation should have. One crucial point that needs to be made in this regard is that the translation teacher needs to take into account the allotted time for his or her lecture. In other words, there should be enough time for translation trainees since training is the most crucial component pupils need to develop their translation skills.

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